

STRESS CONCENTRATION FACTORS OF MATRIX IN COMPOSITE UNDER TRANSVERSE LOADS

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ABSTRACT

Closed-form formulae for stress concentration factors (SCFs) of the matrix in a composite subjected to transverse loads are obtained. In-situ transverse strengths of the matrix, which cannot be measured but must be provided as input data for micromechanical strength prediction of a composite, are assigned as its original counterparts divided by the SCFs. Such a SCF cannot be defined using the maximum stress component on the fiber/matrix interface, as done in the classical definition. It must be determined on an averaged quantity, and is well related to a failure surface of the composite. The failure surface orientation of the composite under a transverse compression is specified through Mohr's failure locus with a parabolic approximation. A simple formula for evaluating the transverse strength of a UD (unidirectional) composite only using its constituent fiber and matrix properties measured independently is thus resulted. Correlation between the evaluated transverse strengths of several UD composites and the available experimental data is very much better if SCFs of the matrices are taken into account than that without an effect of the SCFs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Stress concentration has been a major concern in failure analysis of a solid, in order that its strength can be evaluated through a simple formula of strength of materials. Since the pioneering work of Inglis^[1] on quantitative derivation for a SCF of a plate containing a hole, various discontinuity induced SCFs of homogeneous mainly isotropic materials have been well documented, and have played an important role in an accurate design for the load carrying capacity of a structure. Stress concentrations in heterogenous composites also attract attentions. All these SCFs have been defined essentially following the classical way using a maximum point-wise stress divided by a far-field applied one.

The classical definition, however, is no longer applicable if a composite strength is to be evaluated using a simple formula of strength of materials. Analytical expressions for SCFs of the matrix in a composite subjected to transverse loads are then derived. The motivation of this work is to determine in-situ strengths of the matrix, which are immeasurable but necessary for micromechanical prediction of a composite strength. Although many factors have been attributed to the difference between an in-situ and an original matrix strengths, we believe that a stress concentration due to introduction of fibers is the main reason causing the difference^[2]. Once a SCF is determined, the in-situ strength of the matrix can be assigned as its original counterpart divided by the SCF.

2 HIGHLIGHT ON BRIDGING MODEL

As a SCF is most useful for micromechanical prediction of a composite strength, relevant equations based on Bridging Model^[3] are summarized herein. Due to heterogenous nature, any stress and strain increments in the composite should be defined upon averaged quantities

$$d\sigma_i = \left(\int_V d\tilde{\sigma}_i dV \right) / V' \quad \text{and} \quad d\varepsilon_i = \left(\int_V d\tilde{\varepsilon}_i dV \right) / V' \quad (1)$$

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$$\text{Or,} \quad \{d\sigma_i\} = V_f \{d\sigma_i^f\} + V_m \{d\sigma_i^m\} \quad (2)$$

$$\{d\varepsilon_i\} = V_f \{d\varepsilon_i^f\} + V_m \{d\varepsilon_i^m\} \quad (3)$$

where V_f and $V_m=1-V_f$ are the fiber and matrix volume fractions, respectively.

Suppose that there is a bridging tensor, $[A_{ij}]$, such that

$$\{d\sigma_i^m\} = [A_{ij}]\{d\sigma_j^f\}, \quad (4)$$

which together with Eq. (2) results in

$$\{d\sigma_i^f\} = (V_f[I] + V_m[A_{ij}])^{-1}\{d\sigma_j\} = [B_{ij}]\{d\sigma_j\}, \quad (5)$$

$$\{d\sigma_i^m\} = [A_{ij}][B_{ij}]\{d\sigma_j\}. \quad (6)$$

Closed-form expressions for the elements of $[A_{ij}]$ and $[B_{ij}]$ can be found in [3]. The independent elements of $[A_{ij}]$ are simplified from those of Mori-Tanaka's theory in an elastic region^[3], but result in more accurate predictions for the elastic properties of a UD composite than the latter do^[4-6].

Suppose that a UD composite is only subjected to a transverse (in x_2 -directional) load σ_{22} . Further, both the fiber and the matrix are assumed linearly elastic until rupture. By neglecting an effect of thermal residual stresses, the non-zero stress components in the matrix are found to be^[3]

$$\sigma_{11}^m = \frac{V_f(\nu^m E_{11}^f - \nu_{12}^f E^m)[\beta E_{11}^f E_{22}^f + (1-\beta)E^m E_{11}^f - E^m E_{22}^f]}{(E_{11}^f - E^m)(V_f E_{11}^f + V_m E^m)[(V_f + \beta V_m)E_{22}^f + (1-\beta)V_m E^m]} \sigma_{22}, \quad (7.1)$$

$$\sigma_{22}^m = \frac{\beta E_{22}^f + (1-\beta)E^m}{(V_f + \beta V_m)E_{22}^f + (1-\beta)V_m E^m} \sigma_{22}, \quad (7.2)$$

where E_{11}^f , E_{22}^f and ν_{12}^f are longitudinal modulus, transverse modulus, and longitudinal Poisson's ratio of the fiber respectively, E^m and ν^m are Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the matrix, and β is a bridging parameter to adjust fiber arrangement to some extent^[3]. If no experimental data is available, β can assume a value in between 0.35 to 0.45.

In general, the stress components in the fiber are insignificant under a transverse load, and a composite transverse strength is governed by a matrix failure. Thus, if the maximum normal stress failure criterion is applied, the transverse tensile strength of the composite is given by

$$\sigma_{22}^{u,t} = \frac{(V_f + \beta V_m)E_{22}^f + (1-\beta)V_m E^m}{\beta E_{22}^f + (1-\beta)E^m} Y_m \quad (8)$$

On the other hand, should Tsai-Wu's criterion be applied to govern the matrix failure, the ultimate transverse strength, σ_{22}^u , is calculated from the following condition

$$F_{11}(\sigma_{11}^m)^2 + F_{22}(\sigma_{22}^m)^2 + F_{12}\sigma_{11}^m\sigma_{22}^m + F_1\sigma_{11}^m + F_2\sigma_{22}^m = 1, \quad (9.1)$$

$$F_{11} = \frac{1}{X_m X_m'}, F_{22} = \frac{1}{Y_m Y_m'}, F_{12} = -\sqrt{F_{11} F_{22}}, F_1 = \frac{X_m' - X_m}{X_m X_m'}, F_2 = \frac{Y_m' - Y_m}{Y_m Y_m'}, \quad (9.2)$$

In Eqs. (9.2) and (8), X_m , X_m' , Y_m , and Y_m' are the in-situ strengths of the matrix under longitudinal tension and compression, transverse tension and compression, respectively. They are not equal to the original counterparts, $\sigma_{u,t}^m$ and $\sigma_{u,c}^m$, measured independently using bulk matrix specimens. Otherwise, a predicted transverse tensile strength will be far away from the measured one for any UD composite (see, e.g., **Table 1**). Thus, the in-situ transverse tensile strength of the matrix, Y_m , must have been significantly reduced from its original counterpart, $\sigma_{u,t}^m$, by a SCF.

3 STRESS CONCENTRATION FACTORS

First of all, a SCF of the matrix in a composite cannot be defined as a point-wise stress on the fiber/matrix interface divided by a far-field applied one, since otherwise a crack or debonding on the fiber/matrix interface, which often occurs during fabrication of a composite especially a continuous

fiber reinforced metal matrix composite, would result in an unlimited large SCF and the thus obtained in-situ strength of the matrix would be zero even before any load is applied.

As no point-wise stress is applicable, an averaged quantity should be used. This, however, will bring to us several additional questions. The first question is: with respect to which geometry, a line/curve, a surface, or a volume, should a stress average be done? In view of the fact that a classical SCF is defined as a point-wise stress divided by the far-field applied one which, in fact, is a surface-averaged quantity (averaged with respect to the far-field boundary surface on which the stress is applied), it can be concluded from a rule of similarity that the present SCF should be and can only be defined as a line-averaged stress divided by a volume- averaged quantity.

As such, the second question arises: which straight line should be chosen for the stress average? Experiments show that the failure surface of a UD composite under a transverse compression is in an inclined angle to the loading direction^[7], whereas that under a transverse tension is perpendicular to the tensile load. This strongly suggests that the line for the stress average would be best along the outward normal to a failure surface.

Then, there occurs the last question: how to locate the failure surface of the composite under a transverse compression? Within a cross-sectional plane, a UD composite exhibits an isotropy with a different tensile from compressive strength. Its failure surfaces under tension and compression are different. These characteristics are somewhat similar to the behaviors of an isotropic brittle material. Mohr plotted a series of stress circles each corresponding to a failure stress state of the material. An envelope, called a failure locus envelope, in common contact to these circles can be approximated in a parabolic curve from two failure tests, i.e., uniaxial tension and compression (**Fig. 1**).

Figure 1. A parabolic approximation to the failure locus envelope of an isotropic material

Thus, an inclined angle ϕ of the failure surface under the compression is given by

$$\phi = \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \arcsin \frac{\sigma_{u,c} - \sigma_{u,t}}{2\sigma_{u,c}}$$

Replacing by the composite strength results in
$$\phi = \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \arcsin \frac{\sigma_{22}^{u,c} - \sigma_{22}^{u,t}}{2\sigma_{22}^{u,c}} \quad (10)$$

Substituting Eq. (8) into Eq. (10) leads to

$$\phi = \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \arcsin \frac{Y'_m - Y_m}{2Y'_m} \quad (11)$$

Further simplification is gained by replacing the in-situ with the original strengths in Eq. (11), i.e.,

$$\phi = \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \arcsin \frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{2\sigma_{u,c}^m} \quad (12)$$

A transverse SCF is then defined as
$$K_{22}(\phi) = \frac{1}{\left| \bar{R}_\phi^b - \bar{R}_\phi^a \right|} \int_{\left| \bar{R}_\phi^a \right|}^{\left| \bar{R}_\phi^b \right|} \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^m}{(\sigma_{22}^m)_{BM}} d\left| \bar{R}_\phi \right| \quad (13)$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^m$ is a point-wise stress component in the matrix of a CCA (concentric cylinder assemblage) model along the transverse direction, which can be found in, e.g., Ref. [8], $(\sigma_{22}^m)_{BM}$ is given by Eq. (7.2), and \vec{R}_φ is a vector along a line which has an inclined angle φ with the x_2 direction. \vec{R}_φ^a and \vec{R}_φ^b are the vectors of \vec{R}_φ at the surfaces of the fiber and matrix cylinders. It is noted that the diameters of the fiber and matrix are, respectively, a and $b = a / \sqrt{V_f}$ [2, 8].

After integration, the SCF of the matrix under a transverse tension is obtained as

$$K_{22}^t = K_{22}(0) = \left[1 + \frac{\sqrt{V_f}}{2} A + \frac{\sqrt{V_f}}{2} (3 - V_f - \sqrt{V_f}) B \right] \left[\frac{(V_f + V_m \beta) E_{22}^f + V_m (1 - \beta) E^m}{\beta E_{22}^f + (1 - \beta) E^m} \right] \quad (14)$$

whereas that under a transverse compression is given by

$$K_{22}^c = K_{22}(\phi) = \left\{ 1 - \frac{\sqrt{V_f}}{2} A \frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{2\sigma_{u,c}^m} + \frac{B}{2(1 - \sqrt{V_f})} \left[-V_f^2 \left(1 - 2 \left(\frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{2\sigma_{u,c}^m} \right)^2 \right) + \frac{(\sigma_{u,c}^m + \sigma_{u,t}^m) V_f}{\sigma_{u,c}^m} \left(1 + \frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{\sigma_{u,c}^m} \right) - \sqrt{V_f} \left(\frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{\sigma_{u,c}^m} + 1 - 2 \left(\frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{2\sigma_{u,c}^m} \right)^2 \right) \right] \right\} \times \left[\frac{(V_f + V_m \beta) E_{22}^f + V_m (1 - \beta) E^m}{\beta E_{22}^f + (1 - \beta) E^m} \right] \quad (15)$$

In Eqs. (14) and (15), A and B are read as^[8]

$$A = \frac{[1 - \nu^m - 2(\nu^m)^2] E_{22}^f - [1 - \nu_{23}^f - 2(\nu_{23}^f)^2] E^m}{E_{22}^f (1 + \nu^m) + E^m [1 - \nu_{23}^f - 2(\nu_{23}^f)^2]} \quad (16.1)$$

$$B = \frac{E^m (1 + \nu_{23}^f) - (1 + \nu^m) E_{22}^f}{E_{22}^f [\nu^m + 4(\nu^m)^2 - 3] - E^m (1 + \nu_{23}^f)} \quad (16.2)$$

ν_{23}^f is Poisson's ratio of the fiber in a transverse plane.

4 STRENGTH FORMULAE

The in-situ matrix strengths are assigned as

$$X_m = \sigma_{u,t}^m, X'_m = \sigma_{u,c}^m, S_m = \sigma_{u,s}^m, Y_m = \sigma_{u,t}^m / K_{22}^t, \text{ and } Y'_m = \sigma_{u,c}^m / K_{22}^c \quad (17)$$

A simple formula for evaluating the transverse strength of a UD composite under either a transverse tensile or compressive load is resulted from Eq. (8) as

$$\sigma_{22}^u = \frac{(V_f + 0.4V_m) E_{22}^f + 0.6V_m E^m}{(0.4E_{22}^f + 0.6E^m) K_{22}} \sigma_u^m \quad (18.1)$$

where σ_u^m represents the original tensile or compressive strength of the matrix, and

$$K_{22} = \begin{cases} K_{22}^t, & \text{if } \sigma_{22}^m \geq 0 \\ K_{22}^c, & \text{if } \sigma_{22}^m < 0 \end{cases} \quad (18.2)$$

5 APPLICATION EXAMPLE

Hinton et al. organized a world-wide failure exercise to judge efficiency of the current strength theories for composites. Four pairs of constituent fiber and matrix systems together with the mechanical properties of them and the UD composites made from them were provided^[9]. Those material property parameters are believed to be independently obtained. Only elastic property and

strength data of the constituents were available, which are summarized in **Table 1**. From them, K'_{22} and K^c_{22} are calculated and are listed in the table.

Table 1. Original parameters of four material systems^[9] ($\beta=0.4$)

	AS4/3501-6		T300/BSL914C		E-glass/LY556		E-glass/MY750	
	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix
E_{11} (GPa)	225	4.2	230	4.0	80	3.35	74	3.35
E_{22} (GPa)	15	4.2	15	4.0	80	3.35	74	3.35
ν_{12}	0.2	0.34	0.2	0.35	0.2	0.35	0.2	0.35
G_{12} (GPa)	15	1.567	15	1.481	33.33	1.24	30.8	1.24
G_{23} (GPa)	7	1.567	7	1.481	33.33	1.24	30.8	1.24
$\sigma_{u,t}$ (MPa)	3350	69	2500	75	2150	80	2150	80
$\sigma_{u,c}$ (MPa)	2500	250	2000	150	1450	120	1450	120
V_f	0.60		0.60		0.62		0.60	
K'_{22}	1.899		1.932		2.713		2.658	
K^c_{22}	1.329		1.414		1.828		1.782	

Using the parameters of **Table 1**, the transverse tensile and compressive strengths of the four composites are calculated as per Eqs. (17) and (9). Results are summarized in **Table 2**. Measured data taken from [9] are also shown in the table for comparison. The table clearly demonstrates that without considering a stress concentration in the matrix of a composite, a predicted transverse strength of the composite is totally unacceptable if its original strengths are used in controlling a composite failure, no matter what kind of failure criterion/strength theory is used. Incorporation of a SCF in the prediction can very much improve the correlation accuracy between the theoretical and experimental results.

Table 2. Transverse tensile and compressive strengths (MPa) of four UD composites ($\beta=0.4$)

Strength	AS4/3501-6		T300/BSL914C		E-glass/LY556		E-glass/MY750		
	Y	Y'	Y	Y'	Y	Y'	Y	Y'	
Measured ^[9]	48	200	27	200	35	114	40	145	
Predicted without SCF	By (8)	100	364	110	221	147	221	144	217
	By (9)	85	535	105	296	150	273	148	268
Predicted with SCF	By (8)	53	274	57	156	54	121	54	122
	By (9)	45	350	55	190	54	135	54	136

6 CONCLUSION

Closed-form formulae for SCFs of the matrix in a composite subjected to transverse loads have been derived in this work. Whereas the in-situ longitudinal tensile, compressive, and shear strengths of the matrix can be taken as its original counterparts measured independently, the in-situ transverse tensile and compressive strengths of the matrix are defined as the original ones divided by the obtained SCFs. Using these in-situ strength parameters together with other original constituent properties as input data, the strength of the composite subjected to an arbitrary load condition can be reasonably estimated. This will enable a design for the ultimate load carrying capacity of a structure with composites involved achievable even without anymore experiments on the composites themselves, if a material data bank of constituent fiber and matrix properties is established in advance.

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